

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE SKILLS OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL EDUCATORS

Toymurodova Dilnoza Dilmurodovna

Turon Zarmed University Teacher of the department of preschool
education and sports activities

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7534288>

Abstract. *This article describes the theoretical basis of improving the creative qualities of educators and the methodology of developing creative competence in preschool educational organizations.*

Keywords: *preschool education, future educators, science and education, creativity, professional competence, creative competence, creative potential.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the global tasks of modern innovative development is the formation of creative thinking of people.

Creativity refers to a person's ability to generate new ideas, find solutions to seemingly complex problems, the ability to take risks, a creative approach to his professional activity, and professional maturity. In the processes of the integration of science and education in the globalization of the world, the issue of developing professional preparation of future specialists is defined as one of the urgent tasks.

Modern society requires the education system to educate highly qualified, aspiring, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals.

As a result of the analysis of pedagogical experience and scientific research at the world level, it has been proven that 70% of all the knowledge that a person acquires during his life is acquired by the age of five. In fact, during this period, the child begins to perceive the world, thinks, gets acquainted with the environment, and prepares the ground for the knowledge he will receive throughout his life. Preschool education organizations and specialists of preschool education organizations play an incomparable role in educating the young generation, who are considered the future of our country, as well-rounded individuals.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Among the requirements for the field of education, a number of measures have been implemented to increase the professional and creative competence of specialists of preschool educational organizations. The requirement for a teacher is to conduct research on himself first of all. Therefore, the most important need in the preschool education system is the professional maturity of the specialists of the preschool education organization, as well as the creative competence.

Creativity (lat., eng. "sreate"-creating, "sreative" creator, creator) expresses the meaning of the creative ability of an individual, which describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent.

According to the American psychologist P. Torrens, creativity is a problem or putting forward scientific hypotheses; hypothesis testing and modification; identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results; expresses sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem.

Like any other quality (virtue), creativity is not formed suddenly. Creativity is consistently formed and developed at certain stages.

Possessing creative qualities of a teacher directs his personal abilities, natural and social energy to quality and efficient organization of professional activities. Having creative qualities of pedagogues working in the higher education system helps them to create new ideas different from the traditional approach to the organization of educational and educational processes, not to think in a single mold, originality, initiative, not tolerating uncertainty. Therefore, a creative approach to organizing the professional activity of a pedagogue with creative qualities, activeness in creating new, advanced ideas that serve to develop children's educational activities and personal qualities, independent study of advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences, also focuses on having the experience of continuous, consistent exchange of ideas with colleagues about pedagogical progress. Usually, the ability of pedagogues to have creativity is provided and formed by striving to solve pedagogical problems, carrying out scientific research or scientific projects and achieving mutual creative cooperation, and it gradually improves and develops. As in the case of any specialist, the foundation for future pedagogues' creativity is laid during their student years and is consistently developed in the organization of professional activity. It is important that the pedagogue directs himself to creative activity and is able to organize this activity effectively.

In the organization of creative activity, a teacher should pay special attention to solving problematic issues, analyzing problematic situations, and also creating creative products of a pedagogical nature.

RESEARCH RESULTS

While solving problematic issues and situations, the pedagogue's creative approach to finding a solution to the problem helps him develop emotional and volitional qualities. By putting problematic issues in front of him, the pedagogue confronts the evidence that contradicts his existing knowledge and life experiences. As a result, he feels the need to work on himself, study independently. The pedagogue's scientific and research work and the implementation of scientific or creative projects further develop his creativity potential.

A teacher does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed by consistently studying and working on himself over a period of time.

Modern education requires educators and pedagogues working in all types of educational institutions to be creative.

The concept of "creativity" reflects cultural diversity. For Westerners, creativity is generally considered a novelty. They emphasize that creativity is based on unconventionality, curiosity, imagination, sense of humor, and freedom (Murdoch, Ganim, 1993; Sternberg, 1985). Easterners, on the contrary, understand creativity as a process of rebirth of goodness (Hui, Sternberg, 2002; Rudovich, Hui, 1997; Rudovich, Yuye, 2000). Although Westerners and Easterners have different views on creativity, representatives of both cultures highly value this quality and its possession (Kaufman, Lan, 2012). Many pedagogues-educators believe that they do not have the ability to be creative. This can be justified for two different reasons:

firstly, most pedagogues-educators cannot adequately explain what the concept of "creativity" actually means;

secondly, they are unaware of what qualities are directly reflected in the basis of creativity.

At this point, it is worth noting that every person has the ability to be creative by nature. So, how can they demonstrate their creativity? Here's Patti Drapeau's advice: If you don't think you're creative, I suggest you start organizing creative thinking classes right now. In fact, it is not about whether or not you are creative and creative, but about organizing lessons in the spirit of creativity and trying new ideas in practice.

According to Patti Drapeau, creative thinking is, first of all, comprehensive thinking about a specific issue. Multidisciplinary thinking requires learners to rely on multiple ideas when completing learning assignments, problems, and tasks. In contrast, one-sided thinking is based on only one correct idea.

DISCUSSION

In observation, it is impossible to deny one of the one-sided and multi-sided thinking on the issue. Therefore, one and all-round thinking is equally important in the formation of creativity. That is, when completing a task, solving a problem, the learner looks for several options for a solution (multiple thinking), and then stops at one correct solution that guarantees the most optimal result (unilateral thinking).

Based on the above-mentioned ideas, the concept of "creativity" can be interpreted as follows:

A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific characteristics. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. In addition, creativity determines mental sharpness, "ensures the active involvement of learners in the educational process."

The creativity of the pedagogue is manifested in various forms in professional activity. They are as follows: creative products prepared by a pedagogue-educator based on a creative approach with the help of information, including computer technology, and which can be effectively used in the educational process are listed.

Multimedia is a general concept that applies to computer technologies that transmit information in several forms: graphic, text, digital, sound, music, video, audio, photography, moving images (animations) and other information in electronic form.

An electronic album is a collection in electronic form containing pictures, photos, drawings and graphic images, as well as their annotations. Electronic atlas (Greek "Atlas" - named after the legendary Libyan king who first created a celestial globe) - recommended for a specific educational module (a subject) and has unique graphic images, used for educational purposes.

Digital videos are a modern learning resource in 3D, containing information that helps to acquire knowledge, skills and competences in a learning module (subject).

Virtual booths:

- 1) electronic model of a real object, subject, process, event and events;
- 2) text, picture, scheme, table, diagram, etc. is a computer tool representing the creation, storage, processing, digitization and systematic implementation of information in the form, process and virtual environments.

Simulated virtual simulator (visually "train" - "educate", "train") is an electronic training device that simulates the real conditions of labor activity, certain activities (for example:

(managing a machine (mechanism), working on a complex machine or mastering the secrets of military equipment) are formed, skills are transformed into skills, and the resulting skills are improved.

Multimedia products are development (products) that embody the delivery of educational material to listeners on the basis of audio, video, text, graphic and animation effects based on the software and technical capabilities of ICT.

Audio and video visual materials - materials that provide audio and visual reception of educational information using computer technology.

Video animations are electronic images representing the movement of a drawn (pictured) or small-scale image (volumetric, puppet or toy object) and each step of this movement is filmed sequentially.

Presentation (presentation; Latin "prayeresentatio" - to present) - working papers (plain or watman papers) of materials of an educational (scientific, practical) nature on a specific topic or problem, as well as information and communication tools (computer , projector, processor and other devices).

CONCLUSION

As in the case of any specialist, the foundation for future pedagogues' creativity is laid during their student years and is consistently developed in the organization of professional activity.

It is important that the pedagogue directs himself to creative activity and is able to organize this activity effectively. In the organization of creative activity, a teacher should pay special attention to solving problematic issues, analyzing problematic situations, and also creating creative products of a pedagogical nature.

REFERENCES

1. Allaberganovna, A. F. . (2022). Improvement of the Design of Working Bodies of Modern Presses to Increase Shape-Saving Characteristics During Moisture-Heat Treatment of Clothes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 17–19. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/549>
2. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). Improvement of the Design of Working Bodies of Modern Presses to Increase Shape-Saving Characteristics During Moisture-Heat Treatment of Clothes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 17-19.
3. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). Improvement of the Design of Working Bodies of Modern Presses to Increase Shape-Saving Characteristics During Moisture-Heat Treatment of Clothes. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 28, 17-19.
4. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). KIYIMLARGA NAMLAB-ISITIB ISHLOV BERISHDA SHAKLNI SAQLASH XUSUSIYATINI YAXSHILASH MAQSADIDA ZAMONAVIY PRESSLARNING ISHCHI ORGANLARI KONSTRUKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 117-122.
5. F. Atayeva (2022). KIYIMLARGA NAMLAB-ISITIB ISHLOV BERISHDA SHAKLNI SAQLASH XUSUSIYATINI YAXSHILASH MAQSADIDA ZAMONAVIY PRESSLARNING ISHCHI ORGANLARI KONSTRUKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Science and innovation*, 1 (A5), 221-225. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7050207

6. Allaberganovna, A. F. (2022). KIYIMLARGA NAMLAB-ISITIB ISHLOV BERISHDA SHAKLNI SAQLASH XUSUSIYATINI YAXSHILASH MAQSADIDA ZAMONAVIY PRESSLARNING ISHCHI ORGANLARI KONSTRUKSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(2), 117-122
7. Абдумавлонова Ф. Х., Сейтов А. Ж. СХЕМЫ ГОРНЕРА НА МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОМ ПАКЕТЕ MathCAD //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. CSPI conference 3. – С. 811-816.
8. Сейтов А. Ж., Абдумавлонова Ф. Х. Решение геометрических задач с помощью математического пакета MAPLE //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 933-941.
9. Abdumavlonova F. THE CONCEPT OF THREE-DIMENSIONAL SPACE AND CONSTRUCTION OF VOLUMETRIC BODIES ON THE MATHEMATICAL PACKAGE GEOGEBRA //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 938-950.
10. Salaeva, M. N., Nodirova, Z. Y., Sidiqov, R. R., & Abdumavlonova, F. X. (2021). PISA TADQIQOTIDA KREATIV FIKRLASHNI BAHOLASH MAQSADI VA ASOSIY E'TIBORI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(5), 1358-1364.
11. Сейтов А. Ж., Абдумавлонова Ф. Х. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОГО ПАКЕТА MATHCAD ДЛЯ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ УРОКА НА ТЕМУ «ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫЕ МОДЕЛИ» В 11-КЛАССЕ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 153-160.